

DEVELOPMENT OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION SYSTEM IN PRESCHOOL
EDUCATION

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Abstract: In this article, the new educational system introduced in our country, i.e. the improvement of the inclusive education system, and the introduction of this educational system in pre-school educational organizations, new decisions and decrees have been adopted in order to develop the inclusive education system. , it is said that tasks have been assigned.

Key words: education, education, inclusive, development, improvement, action.

In our country, attention is paid to the education system at the level of state policy. During the past period, on the organization of an effective system of preschool education aimed at bringing the growing generation in our country to a healthy and comprehensively mature adult, introducing effective forms and methods of education and upbringing into the educational process. extensive work has been done. At the same time, the analysis carried out, ensuring children's coverage of preschool education, filling preschool educational institutions with modern educational and methodological materials and fiction, solving the issues of attracting qualified pedagogues and management personnel to the field shows the need. In order to further improve the preschool education system, ensure children's equal use of high-quality preschool education, develop the non-state sector of preschool education services, as well as the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on September 30, 2018 "Management of the Preschool Education System" "On improvement measures" was adopted. In this decision, the concept of developing the preschool education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 was developed. To further improve the normative legal framework in the field of preschool education, to create conditions for the all-round intellectual, moral, aesthetic and physical development of preschool children, to increase the coverage of children with quality preschool education, to ensure equal access to it was held in accordance with the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 29, 2019 "On approval of the concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", the development of inclusive education in Uzbekistan, special educational needs In order to improve the system of education and upbringing of children with special needs and to improve the quality of educational services provided to them, the concept of development of inclusive education in the public education system was developed in 2020-2025.

In 2020-2025, a "road map" was developed for the implementation of the concept of development of inclusive education in the public education system in 2020-2021. The target indicators (indicators) for the development of the education of children with special educational needs until 2025 have been approved. It was determined that the concept will be implemented step by step on the basis of a separate "Roadmap" approved annually starting from 2022, based on the achieved results, target indicators and the main directions for the relevant period. The concept will be implemented in two stages, including: during 2020-2022: improvement of the normative base in the field of inclusive education system; training, retraining and retraining of qualified pedagogues for the inclusive education system; strengthening the material and technical base of

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institutions where inclusive education is introduced, providing them with special devices (lifting devices, ramps, handrails, etc.), necessary literature, methodical manuals, equipment and supplies for training in various professions ; introduction of modern information and communication technologies and innovative projects in the field of inclusive education; creating a positive social environment among the population by explaining the right to education of children with special educational needs, the essence of inclusive education; implementation of measures aimed at preventing discrimination of children with special educational needs, negative treatment of them; introduction of the inclusive education system into the activities of individual educational institutions as an experiment; During 2023 — 2025: gradual introduction of the inclusive education system in other general secondary education institutions; implementation of measures aimed at ensuring the right to inclusive education of every child with special educational needs; teaching methods in inclusive education are improved and the principles of individualization are gradually introduced into the educational process; In the process of inclusive education, it is aimed at the spiritual and moral education of students, and their physical, healthy and energetic formation, teaching methods in inclusive education are improved and the principles of individualization are gradually introduced into the educational process; in the process of inclusive education, taking measures aimed at the spiritual and moral upbringing of students, their physical healthy and energetic formation; optimization of the number of specialized state educational institutions for children with special educational needs was determined based on the physical and mental needs of students and the geographical location of educational institutions.

OUTCOME. The mission of inclusive education is to provide quality education to all children, regardless of their abilities and status. At the same time, the principle of inclusion implies that children with limited opportunities should live in a family and receive education in a normal school together with their peers in order to have a positive mental and social development. The inclusive education system means that a child in a wheelchair can study in any nearby school, if he/she has learning difficulties, he/she has special help to learn to read and write, and a child who does not attend classes ensures that appropriate support is provided to return to school.

CONCLUSION. The importance of inclusive education in the pre-school education system is the development of mental and physical emotions and movements of the child, ensuring that children with disabilities are included in the ranks of healthy children from an early age and receive quality education. What does inclusive education provide to children with disabilities? - allows one to discover one's own opportunities for oneself - independent movement occurs through the opportunity to work together, in cooperation; -worldview expands, life experience increases; - the need and interest in studying increases; -He begins to feel the same as everyone else; - Unexpected opportunities will open up; -Features such as bed rest and isolation will disappear. How does inclusive education affect the lives of healthy children? - They feel their peers who are not like them and their life and needs; - The feeling of caring for peers is awakened; - To support them, to try to help them - a sense of humanity is cultivated; -Students develop a positive attitude and mutual respect towards people around them, people with disabilities -They become people who do not neglect people in need.

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